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Distributional Pattern and Literacy Status of Katakari Tribes in Raigad District of Maharashtra: A Geographical Perspective

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Abstract

The Katakari are a tribal group of indigenous hunter gatherers who live in the Indian state of Maharashtra. Their ongoing survival is threatened by years of systemic exploitation, racial prejudice, abject poverty and loss of their traditional lands. The Katakari people are an Indian Hindu community mostly belonging to the state of Maharashtra. They have been categorized as a scheduled tribe. Other names and spellings include Katakari, Kothari and kathodia they are bilingual speaking the Katakari language in the dialect and Marathi language as regular for other than Katakari. Literacy is one of the important indices of development of any community in any region. But for the backward communities especially for tribals it is a stepping stone for their development, without which the progress is just impossible. Therefore the educational and literacy level of the Katakari community is concern it should be assess and find out the ground reality. As per 2001 census the literacy rate of the district was 45.05 percent, it slightly lower than the other district because these area having tribal people. The maximum literacy rate 63.97 percent was shown in the Murud Tahsil and the minimum was 25.07 in Managaon Tahsil these Tahsil represent very low literacy rate because these area tribal population living and average literacy rate of district about 44.68 percent. The male average literacy of sample village is more than 27 percent (27.2%), and average gender gap is about 5.73 percent. While female average literacy depicted 21.42 percent. Further the educational attainment and enrollment was also very average as per Katakari are concern.

Key words: Katakari, literacy, education, attainment, enrollment

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Introduction:

The Katakari are a tribal group of indigenous hunter gatherers who live in the Indian state of Maharashtra. Their ongoing survival is threatened by years of systemic exploitation, racial prejudice, abject poverty and loss of their traditional lands.

The Katakari people are an Indian Hindu community mostly belonging to the state of Maharashtra. They have been categorized as a scheduled tribe. Other names and spellings include Katakari, Kothari and kathodia they are bilingual speaking the Katakari language in the dialect and Marathi language as regular for other than Katakari.

The Katakari were at one time a forest people living in the “Western Ghats” of Maharashtra, with a special relationship to forest creatures such as the tiger hunter means waghmare.

The name Katakari is derived from a forest based activity, the making and sale of catechu (katha) from the khair tree (acacia catechu). Katakari were thinker scattered in small communities throughout the hill ranges and forest of Raigad and Thane districts of the state of Maharashtra, some also lived in hill areas in the southern part of the current state of Gujarat and in the forest of what are now Nasik Pune & Dhulia districts.

The Katakari population engaged in a wild range of livelihoods including the production and sale of catechu, charcoal, firewood, and other forest product. Freshwater fishing, hunting of small mammals and bird's upland agriculture and agriculture labor on the farms these few options but to move seasonally in search of employment and new place to live.

Beginning in the 1950's Katakari families began to migrate permanently form ancestral area in the hill to out karts of agricultural villages on the plains, and many very small Katakari hamlets are now spread throughout the region Khalapur, Sudhagad, Karjat, pen, Panvel Tahsils of the Raigad district and various Tahsils in thane district, right up to outskirts of Mumbai.

Present circumstances

At present the Katakari's are fragmented and very scattered community highly dependent on other form of their livelihood and for a place to live. Most Katakari's are landless workers with only periodic and tenuous connection to their original nomadic forest based live ads many have become borne labors working on the brick kilns and charcoal units serving the urban and industrial interests of greater Mumbai.

The every 3rd of the Katakari hamlets located in Raigad and thane district are on private as well as on Government lands, outside of the villages. The Katakari struggles to ream in their hamlets provides an important contrast to the land tenure problems facing urban slum dwellers.

STUDY AREA

For the present study the Raigad district is selected to look into the distributional pattern with their educational and literacy status of Katakari tribals. The geographical position of district in state of Maharashtra is on the Western part and it is part of Deccan Plateau. Population of Raigad district according to 2011 census is of 26, 34,200, (22, 07,929 population in 2001 census).

Form the location point of view, the district is extents between 17° 51' to 19° 80' north latitude, and 72° 51' to 73° 40' east longitude. The Raigad district has an area of 7152 sq. km. it is

bounded by Thane to the north and Ratnagiri district to the south, Pune district lies to its east and Satara district to its south-east on the west coast the district is bounded by Arabian Sea.

The district has 15 Tahsils with four administrative division's viz. Alibagh, Panvel, Mahad and Managaon.

For the present study the following 12 case study villages are selected from four Tahsils of Raigad district viz. Sudhagad, Managaon, Mahad, and Poladpur and collected first hand information to know the ground reality through filling the household schedules.

Table, 1

SURVEYED TRIBAL POPULATION AND HOUSEHOLDS TO TOTAL IN SAMPLE VILLAGES, 2014

Sr. No	Name of Village	Name of Tahsil	Name of District	Total House holds	Surveyed Households	Total Population	Surveyed Population	% of Surveyed Households to Total Households	% of Surveyed Population to Total Population
1	Zapwadi	Sudhagad	Raigad	38	11	235	59	28.95	25.11
2	Wavloli	Sudhagadh	Raigad	35	11	156	44	31.43	28.20
3	Rabgaon	Sudhagadh	Raigad	38	12	228	69	31.58	38.30
4	Sidheshwar wadi	Sudhagadh	Raigad	48	31	288	131	64.58	45.49
5	Nandavi Wadi	Managaon	Raigad	53	17	224	84	32.07	37.50
6	Madegaon	Managaon	Raigad	110	21	490	107	19.09	21.84
7	Chambarkhind	Mahad	Raigad	14	7	84	45	50.00	53.57
8	Kharab wadi	Mahad	Raigad	32	5	192	27	16.13	14.06
9	Virthembu	Mahad	Raigad	45	9	270	36	20.00	13.33
10	Virthembe wadi	Mahad	Raigad	29	13	174	75	44.83	43.10
11	Lohar mala	Poladpur	Raigad	48	15	288	66	31.25	22.92
12	Non tribals	Poladpuir	Raigad	45	17	270	89	37.78	32.96
	Total			535	169	2899	832	33.97	31.37

Source-Field Survey Feb-2014

Objective

The main objective of the present study is to examine the distributional pattern and literacy and educational level of Katakari tribal's.

Data Base and methodology

In order to meet the objectives of the study is mainly based on primacy data which have been collected by conducting the intensive fieldwork in the selected 15th tribal villages in the district. The 169 houses were surveyed out of these 15 villages which constituted about 33.97 percent of the total household.

Systematic sampling technique was applied for the collection of primary data every villages was entirely Katakari Tribal's villages and having homogenous groups. Therefore the question of applying stratified sampling was also more or also the same.

After the collection of data various statistical techniques have been employed. Literacy is calculated as follow.

$$\text{Literacy rate} = \frac{\text{Literate population of Tahsils/Tribe}}{\text{Total population above 6 age}} \times 100$$

Percentage of tribal population to the total population in the taluka or village is computed. Levels of educational attainments at primary (4th std.) middle Primary (7th std.) S.S.C and high secondary, for this the above 6 age of population have been calculated.

Secondary data has been collected form district census hand book of Raigad district, Review of Socio-Economic report of Raigad district other necessary information also collected form of primary school, village accountant, Gram Sevak, Villagers, Internet etc. Collected data analyzed by using appropriate techniques and methods and tabulated accordingly. Wherever necessary the map graphs are also prepared maps and graphs by using various cartographic techniques.

The Discussion

Literacy is one of the important indices of development of any community in any region. But for the backward communities especially for tribals it is a stepping stone for their development, without which the progress is just impossible. As per the census of India 2011, a literate person is he or she who can both read and write with understanding in any language is considered a literate person. It is not binding that he or she must have taken the formal education; it can be acquired informally also. Any literate person can protect him or her from exploitation by others. It also brings improvement and comprehensive to participate in

advancing World. It helps to bring development in almost all sectors of economy. In the general population the literacy rate was quite good, but in case of Katakari tribes the literacy attainment is comparatively very low. Still there is a mass illiteracy among them if we look into their literacy as per our field study.

Literacy at Tehsils level

As per 2001 census the literacy rate of the district was 45.05 percent, it slightly lower than the other district because these area having tribal people. Tribal people leaving in Raigad district these people not give wet to the education. Literacy rate totally depend upon educational level.

The maximum literacy rate 63.97 percent was shown in the Murud Tahsil and the minimum was 25.07 in Managaon Tahsil these Tahsil represent very low literacy rate because these area tribal population living and average literacy rate of district about 44.68 percent.

Table, 2

Percentage of Tahsil wise literacy Rate of Raigad District, 2001

Sr,no	Tahsil	Literacy Rate		
		Total	Male	Female
1.	Uran	63.40	73.56	52.92
2.	Panyel	44.53	55.14	33.51
3.	Karjat	42.42	54.34	30.16
4.	Khalapur	33.04	42.67	23.06
5.	Pen	33.76	43.07	24.16
6.	Alibag	61.67	73.24	50.09
7.	Murad	63.97	74.69	53.55
8.	Roha	49.88	59.43	40.00
9.	Sudhagad	30.89	40.45	20.88
10.	Mangaon	25.07	32.58	17.42
11.	Tala	38.30	47.21	30.40

12.	Shrivadhan	55.53	70.94	41.32
13.	Mhasal	53.36	66.30	42.38
14.	Mahad	35.82	45.12	25.74
15.	Poladpur	38.29	45.95	30.34
Raigarh district		45.05	55.49	34.44

Source-Census of India-2011

Literacy of Village Level

The government of India and Maharashtra has taken special interest in tribal education to enhance their status in literacy and education during last two decades. Large of 'Ashram schools' has been started in the tribal areas, Raigad is a coastal district situated on the West coast, these area rugged and full of forest, on the top of hill, slope and at foothills where they gets open lands where they settled down, they also face to the problem of educational facility. But now some extend this problem is cure due to education and educational package provides by government. Ashram schools have been established in this area. Katakari tribe they can gets lodging and boarding stationary school uniform, book etc.

Table, 3

Literacy level of Katakari tribe in sample village-2014

Sr. No	Name of village	Male	female	Total	Gender gap rate
1	Zapwadi	29.62	27.77	57.4	1.85
2	Wavloli	20.45	13.63	34.09	6.82
3	Rabgaon	24.59	19.67	44.37	4.92
4	Sidheshwar wadi	30.54	16.03	46.56	14.51
5	Nandavi	32.43	31.08	63.51	1.35
6	Madegaon	27.55	25.51	53.06	2.04
7	Chambarkhind	29.62	22.22	51.85	7.04
8	Kharb wadi	23.07	19.23	42.4	3.84

9	Virthembu	18.18	9.09	27.27	9.09
10	Virthembu wadi	24.19	16.12	40.32	8.08
11	Loharmala	37.28	35.59	72.88	1.59
12	Non tribal	28.88	21.11	50	7.7
	Average	27.2	21.42	48.64	5.73

Source-Field Survey Feb-2014

Literacy level of Katakari tribe in sample village-2014

Male – Female Literacy

The male average literacy of sample village is more than 27 percent (27.2%), and average gender gap is about 5.73 percent. While female average literacy depicted 21.42 percent. The maximum male literacy was noted in Lohar Mala I.e. 37.28 percent and minimum in Virthembu is less than 19 percent (18.18%). The followed by Nandaviwadi 32.43%, Sidheshwar wadi 30.54%, Wavlioli 20.45%, Zapwadi 29.62%, Rabgaon 24.59%, Madhegaon is 27.55%, Chambarkhind 29.07%, and Virthembewadi 24.19%, Where the non tribal villages having medium level literacy rate. The mass literacy among woman in the study are is noted that, the maximum literacy of female was 35.59 percent in LoharMala these having both males and

female literate population and minimum literacy of female 9.09 in Virthembu, and the gender gap showing between male and female in literacy is very minor i.e. 5.73 percent in these villages. The positive gender literacy gap is found in all village. Male are more educated, here the Lohar Mala, Nandviwadi and Sidheshwar wadi boy are more to taking education in ashram schools.

Levels of Educational attainment of Village level

All this very truly indicates that where the Ashram Shala or Zillah Parishad Schools are near the Katakari Village and Pada, the proportion of educational level is more. In the sample village no single member is found in enrolled in higher education i.e. at HSC, Graduation and Post graduation level, only few male are going outside for higher education but females are left behind in house, because of insecurity and poor mentality of their people. The college facilities are not available in village. They go taking higher education in Tehsil place at distance of 20km from village.

Table, 4

Status of Education attainment of Katakari tribe in sample village 2014

Sr.no	Village name	Primary	M. primary	Secondary	H.S.C	G.D	P.G
		4 th	7 th	10 th	12 th		
	Zapwadi	41.17	58.82	52.94	5.88	-	-
	Wavloli	32.25	38.70	29.03	3.22	-	-
	Rabgaon	28	24	40	0.8	-	-
	Sidheshwar wadi	28.92	31.88	18.88	5.79	-	-
	Nandavi	40.90	31.81	25	2.27	-	-
	Madegaon	35.71	23.88	38.09	2.38	-	-
	Chamberkhind	64.28	21.42	14.28	-	-	-
	Kharb wadi	50	25	2.08	16.66	-	-
	Virthembu	44.44	44.44	11.11	-	-	-
	Virthembu wadi	57.14	14.28	28.57	-	-	-

	Loharmala	26.82	29.26	26.82	17.07	-	-
	Non tribal	19.35	32.25	32.25	9.67	6.45	-
	Average	39.08	31.31	28.81	7.082	6.45	

Source-Field Survey Feb-2014

Primary Education Level

The levels of education attainment among the Katkari tribe in sample village is quite, due to state government policy is to cover the small villages through one teacher. School at primary level the average 4th std pass was 39.08 percent. The maximum boys and girls studding and pass out the 4th std in chambarkhind 64.28% and the minimum student 4th std pass parlewadi is 19.35%, because of primary school facility are available in village level in katkari village each village not provide to the primary school. Some villages are available primary school in these tribe primary level educational attempt is much higher than the female children.

Middle Educational Level

The proportion of middle level average is 31.31% and above average literacy 2 village Zapwadi 58.82 and Virthembu 44.44 percent and below average Virthembe wadi 14.28 percent, and Chambarkhind is 21.42%. It seen that where or near by the village Ashrams shala is male and female are available middle primary education is relatively high than the primary education.

S.S.C Level

At S.S.C level also average 28.8% tribal are 10th pass. The highest katkari tribal in 10th pass are found in Rabgavwaadi 40% and Virthembu 11.11% , Virthembe wadi 28.57% and Chamberkhind 14.28% in Zapwadi their 52.94% , Wavloli 29.03%, Sidheshwar wadi 18.88%, Nandvi 25%, Madegaon 16%, Chambarkhind in 14.28%, Virkharb wadi having very low percent to pass the 10th std. Loharmala and Parlewadi and that's are 26.82 and 32.25 respectively.

The S.S.C level proportion of female is less than male. The disparity between male and female is quite high. In these eleven and one is non tribal village's not available secondary school facility near by the jurisdiction.

H.S.C Level

The higher secondary education facility was not available in these tribal villages. The high school and higher secondary education facilities are only looking at the Tehsil place. In

katkari tribe 12th std pass maximum rate in Virkhrab wadi having 16.66 % people passed 12th std and minimum population studying in Rabgaon wadi only 0.8% , Chambarkhind , %Virthembu and virthembu wadi there is on any population studying in 12th std, and Average population passed in 12th std in various village is 7.8 2%.

Graduation and post-graduation level

These entire surveyed tribal village having education facilities are very low. In this surveyed village only 4 people passed and complete the under graduation education. Katakari tribal students are unable to take Graduation and Post graduation education due to weak economic condition and lack of facilities. There after the 10th and 12th class education completes, student joins the job especially in Brick kilns, they engage in wood cutting in the forest, occupation so they student not get under graduation and post-graduation level education. So, only very few person are going cut to graduation and post- graduation level.

Government primary school and ashram school have provide to be providing better quality education and other basic amenities to the treble children, there is still the problem of drop out both in Zillaparishad school and, Ashram School in tribal areas. Early age of marriage of male and female. Most of male and female do not like to attend school to marry between 18 to 20. The tribal male are upon economic responsibility in all family so they are cause of the Katkari tribal male and female do not go to the taking graduation post-graduation Level education.

Enrollment rate

Enrollment of children of society reflects the development and understanding of the people regarding education attainment. The parents who are conscious about education of their children they make it tangible at any cast to sent to then school. Tribal little and small girls and boys not got the school they play in home so, their Enrollment Rate is very low.

At district level the enrollment condition is showing in below table that the average enrollment at 12th standard was only 5.33 per cent in 2011. At 7th std. it was high as 13.08 per cent, and at other all standards the average was remains between 7 to 13 per cent.

As per as tahsil level is concern, the maximum level of enrollment was 15.97 per cent at 7th std. in Pen tahsil. In Sudhagad tahsil it was 12.76 per cent, where high concentration of tribals was noticed.

Table, 5

Percentage of Educational Enrollment of Raigad district, 2011

Sr,no	Tahsil	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th	12 th
1.	Uran	9.23	9.40	10.08	9.44	3.76	4.32	16.90	8.83	9.00	6.06	6.12	6.42
2.	Panvel	7.80	7.87	7.73	7.43	8.42	8.57	10.32	10.24	10.18	9.42	6.16	5.86
3.	Karjat	9.36	9.51	8.82	8.66	9.00	8.73	12.86	7.57	7.20	4.09	7.31	8.31
4.	Khalapur	8.62	9.56	9.58	9.39	8.66	8.62	13.84	7.63	7.61	5.25	6.10	6.01
5.	Pen	8.34	8.80	7.68	7.56	9.36	10.21	15.97	7.61	4.24	10.30	8.76	4.82
6.	Alibag	7.97	8.79	8.34	8.34	8.00	8.07	15.32	8.52	9.02	7.32	5.11	4.73
7.	Murad	7.35	8.41	9.69	10.08	6.07	5.87	13.64	10.89	11.10	7.81	4.85	4.20
8.	Roha	7.81	8.54	9.26	8.46	8.09	8.46	13.63	8.77	9.11	8.15	6.12	3.57
9.	Sudhagad	9.42	11.43	12.56	9.23	4.77	3.73	12.76	9.31	8.69	7.82	8.67	4.53
10.	Mangaon	7.37	8.09	8.72	8.37	8.24	8.81	8.76	10.06	9.54	7.27	9.54	6.30
11.	Tala	6.84	7.41	7.85	8.16	6.57	6.16	15.77	12.05	9.95	8.85	4.95	5.75
12.	Shrivadhan	6.79	7.29	8.61	8.33	4.72	4.39	13.97	9.92	11.80	11.81	6.29	6.09
13.	Mhasal	7.40	7.85	7.83	8.14	6.33	6.39	12.17	10.88	10.59	9.49	6.48	5.83
14.	Mahad	7.61	0.09	7.91	8.21	8.36	7.72	11.54	11.19	11.85	10.23	4.20	2.89
15.	Poladpur	6.70	7.66	9.85	9.83	10.09	10.34	8.78	9.59	9.28	8.88	4.46	4.46
	Average	7.91	8.05	8.97	8.64	7.36	7.36	13.08	9.54	9.28	8.18	6.34	5.32

Source-Census of India-2011

Table, 6

Percentage of Enrollment Rate Katakari tribe in the study area 2014
 Source: Field Study, 2014

Sr. no	Village name	Primary	M. primary	Drop Out	Secondary	H.S.C	Drop Out	G.D	P.G
Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal (AMIERJ) (Bi-Monthly) Peer-Reviewed Journal Vol No III Issues II ISSN 2278-5655									
	Standard --->	1 to 4	5 to 7		8 to 10	11 to			
						12			
1	Zapwadi	7.6	46.15	-38.55	38.46	7.6	30.86	-	-
2	Wavloli	14.28	88.71	-74.43	-	-	-	-	-
3	Rabgaon	46.15	7.6	+38.55	38.46	7.6	30.86	-	-
4	Sidheshwar wadi	38.88	30.55	+8.33	19.44	11.11	+8.33	-	-
5	Nandavi	61.90	28.57	+33.33	4.76	4.76	-	-	-
6	Madegaon	35.48	22.58	+12.09	38.07	3.22	+35.48	-	-
7	Chamberkhind	50	25	+25	25	-	+25	-	-
8	Kharb wadi	-	50	-50	25	25	-	-	-
9	Virthembu	50	33.33	+16.57	16.66	-	+16.66	-	-
10	Virthembu wadi	61.11	-	+61.11	38.88	-	+38.88	-	-
11	Loharmala	54.54	13.63	+40.91	27.27	4.54	+22.73	-	-
12	Non tribal	22.84	20	+2.84	25.71	20	+5.71	8.57	2.85
	Average	40.25	33.28	6.31	27.06	10.47	23.83	8.57	2.85

Enrollment at village level

Primary Level

The enrollment ratio rate's from primary educational level the maximum enrollment rate in Lohar Mala. These village having a 54.54 percent primary level of enrollment and average 40.25 children are gating only primary level education and minimum enrollment rate of Zapwadi is 7.6 percent in these tribal group primary level of 6 – 10 age group all should get enrolled in the 5th school but it has not happened even in and remaining. Wavloli 14.28%, Rabgaon 46.15%, Sidheshwar wadi 38.88%, Nandaviwadi 61.90% highest primary level enrolled rate. Madegaon 35.48, Chambarkind 50% in Kharab wadi they have no any one person or male and female studding in primary level them all studying in middle primary school.

Virthembu 50%, and Lohar Mala, Virthembe wadi and Non tribal's village having 54.54, 61.11, and 22.84 primary education levels respectively.

Middle Primary Level

The middle primary level enrollment ratio less and lowest than the primary level because very few student go to the middle primary gating education and average enrollment ratio having Wavloli 88.71%, the middle primary level and primary level education dropout rate was very minor means 6.31%. Positive dropout rate was very high in Rabgon i.e. + 38.55%.

Secondary Level

At secondary level them to last one is the secondary level average enrollment ratio is 27.06% these ratio have to reduces primary to middle primary to secondary level. Secondary level and HSC level education dropout rate very high 23.83% because the school is normally located at long distance place from the village.

Higher Secondary Level

At highest secondary level also the enrolled the hardly one village means non tribal student gating higher secondary level education and average of the higher secondary level education ratio is very low is 10.47% other than all primary to secondary level. These two step mean secondary and higher secondary level dropout rate very highest is 23.83 in Virthembewadi they very highest population dropout rate 38.80. Because the drop out by student in economic ability of the parent's to meet the educational needs of the children.

Graduation and P. G. Level

The Katakari tribal population no anyone to the getting graduation and P. G. level education in surveyed village only 8.57%, 2.85% population gating the graduation and P. G. level education in non tribal village among the all eleven villages non was enrolled for graduation neither the facility nor their economic educational attainment among the tribals.

Their for action needs to be taken not only for strengthening the ongoing programmers, but also for taking additional steps to tacked the persistent problem of low literacy, high dry out rates through easy access to residential schools, school autonomy, supervision and co-ordination by the village educational committee and other facilities like hostel for tribal female, extension of incentives like scholarships, free books, uniforms etc. A perform this is also indispensable for importing education relating to human rights. This will develop all sorts of consciousness and bring prosperity and progress in the sector. Condition allows to get enrolled. At post graduation level on an average the enrollment is hardly 8.57 graduation levels and 2.85 percent only P. G. level, and dropped out rate is very is Katkari tribe.

Conclusion

The present study is based on primary as well as secondary sources of data. Primary data are collected through the field survey and secondary sources of data is obtained from the census of India, and review of socio-economic survey – 2001 conducted by Zillah Parishad Raigad. “Arthik Samolachan of “Raigad District” 2011 – 2012 to analyze to distribution and literacy status or general population is connection with to understand the present distribution and literacy status of Katakari tribe in sample village. The primary data is collected by conducting the intensive field survey in Feb, 2014. These sample villages are Zapwadi, Wavloli, Sidheshwar and Rabgaon this village in Sudhagad Tehsil, then Nandaviwadi, Madegaon, Chambarkhind, Kharabwadi, Virthembu, Virthembewadi in Mangaon and Mahad Tehsil these villages located near the foot of the hill and on the hill and forest area. These village and Wadi’s and Pada’s having very less number in houses therefore we taking about 12 small wadi and Pada’s for the saks of study. These 12 Pada’s and small Wadi are into sample village. These are from Sudhagad, Managaon, Mahad and Poladpur Tehsil in Raigad district. The primary data was collected to bring out hidden ground realities regarding their housing condition and literacy status of Katakari tribes is the district on the basis of this the pervious chapter’s are concluded as follow’s .

The average literacy rate of district is (44.68%) it is slightly lower than the state and country average literacy rate; it means that the district is having good performance, in literacy rate in general population. In the Tahsil or Murud and Alibag having comparatively good average literacy rate that is (63.97%) and (61.67%) respectively. But at the sample villages, this proportion was very low at educational attainment. Because there is not good available education facility in Raigad districts some Tahsil having well among the male and female literacy rate. The average literacy rate of male and female is (55.01%) and (34.39%) respectively and the average gender gap of Raigad district is 24.36% these rate is very low compare to the other district in surveyed Katakari tribal community literacy level and literacy rate is very low because there is not available school or college and economic status and education background in surveyed village there is four Tahsil some selective Katakari village there are 11 tribal (Katakari) and 1 is non tribal village literacy in that village non tribal village literacy rate is very high other than in Katakari village the total average literacy rate is (48.64%) and the male compare to the female literacy rate is very low is (21.42%) male is (27.2%) and the

very high literacy level in Lohar mala and minimum literacy rate is Virthembu village that is (27.27%) and the average gender gap is (5.73%) in Virthembu village very high gender gap is (9.09%).

The educational status of these sample village was very poor, as per our survey conducted in Feb -2014. No any person has found beyond 10th pass. In sample villages, there is a maximum peoples are at level of 4th and 7th standard in 11 village. The average educational level at 4th standard pass was 39.08 per cent and followed 31.31% 7th pass, and 28.81 10th pass, and 7.82% were 12th pass, and no any one person not to get Graduation and PG level education, where non tribal village is well developed in education as compare to the tribal village, so the it needs to gate awareness in Katakari tribe community. As per the enrollment ratio is concern up to graduation level the proportion is very less, where the average enrollment was looking in these villages. At the primary level (up to 4th) the average enrollment (40.25%) and maximum is of (61.61%) Nandaviwadi in Managaon Tahsil and minimum in Zapwadi (7.6) in Sudhagad Tahsil in same education enrollment in middle primary level the average (33.28%) and heist enrollment having village is Wavloli (88.71%) and very low only (7.6%) in Rabgaon and the where average gender gap is (6.31%) all village in middle primary level, where very high dropout rate in Wavloli (+38.55%), and very low dropout rate in Rabgaon. Then the secondary level the average enrollment rate is (27.06%) and HSC level average enrollment rate also low is (10.47%) the two stages secondary and HSC level dropout rate was more increase (23.83%) of at all village, and on the contrary the non tribal villages the graduation and PG level dropout rate very low because of the richness and vision of education. The Katakari tribe enrollment rate is very poor and it needs to increase this enrollment ratio by providing educational as well as other facilities like boarding, scholarships, fellowships etc.

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